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REMOTE ACCESS AND CONTROL MOBILE PHONE USING SMS

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Abstract-Among people the mobile phone usage is increasing rapidly. The mobile phones have more popularity in their usage for accessing internet like mail accessing, online shopping, e-banking and social networking. In previous applications you need an Internet access but now with this application you can remotely control your mobile phone without internet. Given the features problem arises if the phone is left at someplace and we want to retrieve some information from the mobile phone. In such cases remotely accessing of mobile phone is necessary. For this problem, we thought of developing an application which allows remote accessing through SMS. It includes retrieving the IMEI number of the mobile phone, accessing contact number from the phone book, changing profile settings, etc.

Keywords- Short message service (SMS), remote access, mobile communication, control commands.

INTRODUCTION

Smartphone's contains data of users like call records, contacts, photos, videos, messages, and emails. Previously manufactures of all mobile phone have dedicated application to control android phones to android phones through internet. This is the biggest disadvantages of previous system. In our proposed application we remove the disadvantage of previous system. And we develop this application which works without internet or without internet we can control our android phone remotely. Our project is an android application which is developed to perform different tasks on your mobile phone from any other phone via simple SMS, and control your android phone remotely using SMS. The basic purpose of this application is, if we have forgotten our android phone at any place we can still control that phone remotely by sending an SMS.

Problem Description-

“Remote access & control of mobile phone using SMS” is an android application which is developed to perform various tasks on your phone from any other simple phone via simple SMS, and control your android phone remotely using SMS. The main purpose of this application is, if we forgotten our mobile phone at any place then also you can control that phone. You can access & retrieve a lot of data from your mobile phone. If

you are using an android device, then you can change the settings remotely just through an SMS.

Proposed system-

If you have forgotten your mobile phone at any place and you need to call a person urgently whose contact number is not available at that time it is not possible to go there and take mobile phone immediately. It takes lot of time. In this case, the users will communicate directly with mobile phone through SMS. In this process one can send an SMS from someone's mobile phone to his/her own mobile phone command syntax.

E.g. CMD RINGER VIBRATE

If you wish to vibrate your mobile phone from normal or silent mode at that time you can send this command.

E.g. CMD IMEI

If you want to get yours mobile IMEI number then this command is used.

Architecture-

“Remote access and control of mobile phone using SMS” is an android application. It is developed to perform different tasks on your mobile phone from any other phone through SMS, and control your mobile phone remotely. The main purpose of this application is, if we forgotten our mobile phone at any place then also you can control that phone remotely. You can access & retrieve a lot of data from your mobile phone like Messages, Contact details, Call logs, IMEI number.

The actual working of this application is shows in this diagram. User sends a request as a SMS to the system. System processes that request and send response in the form of command back to the user. User should choose command from the command list and response again to the system. System takes that command, performs it and sends output to the user.

The command list contains following forms:

K.E. Society's

1. CMD RINGER
2. CMD IMEI
3. CMD CONTACT

1. CMD RINGER:
 Send this command to mobile phone then profile of our mobile phone change from silent to normal and vice versa.

Remote device:

Eg. CMD RINGER SILENT

Mobile device send:

Profile is changed.

2. CMD IMEI:

Send this command to mobile phone then we get IMEI of our phone.

Remote device:

Eg. CMD IMEI

Mobile device send:

345378367868792

3. CMD CONTACT:

Send this command to mobile phone with name of person and we get contact number.

Remote device:

Eg. CMD CONTACT ABC

Mobile device send:

ABC-9562874163

Flowchart-

CONCLUSION

The proposed application has been implemented in android operating system. The application can be implemented in other Smartphone platforms. This Application is very useful in case, If we have forgotten, misplaced, lost our android phone. We control phone remotely through SMS and the apps reacts to that command. Whenever you forget your mobile phone at any place. Send a SMS to your mobile number with the Security password to access and control your Android Device. Suppose your mobile is on normal mode and you have to change on vibrate mode then you can send the command 'CMD HELP PASSWORD' then that gives you reply with command list. You need to choose one command from the list and send it. Then your mobile works as per the command and gives reply.

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